

Hardware-Friendly Random Forest Classification of iEEG Signals for Implantable Seizure Detection

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Abstract—Early and accurate detection of epileptic seizures is an extremely important therapeutic goal due to the severity of complications it can prevent. To this end, a low-power machine learning-based seizure detection implemented on an FPGA is proposed in this paper. Feature extraction is performed using time domain features which exhibit low hardware implementation complexity as well as high classification performance. A comparison between a Random Forest and a linear Support Vector Machine classifier has been conducted leading to the superior performance of the Random Forest. In addition, the hyperparameters of the Random Forest classifier are optimized to reach the best classification performance as well as to maintain the hardware implementation complexity sufficiently low for medical devices implants. The proposed seizure detector is implemented on a Cyclone V FPGA of the ALTERA DE10-standard board and tested on iEEG signals of six patients from the Bern University Hospital. FPGA implementation results demonstrate 100% seizure detection sensitivity as well as better specificity and faster seizure detection compared to recently published works using random forest classification. The FPGA dynamic power consumption is 0.59 mW which is acceptable for low-power implantable devices.

Index Terms—Biomedical digital signal processing, Random Forest classifier, Epileptic seizure detection, iEEG feature extraction.

I. INTRODUCTION

Patients who suffer from epilepsy often experience recurrent seizures, which are defined as episodes of excessive or abnormal synchronous neuronal activity in the brain [1]. Seizure characteristics vary widely from patient to patient, and even within an individual from seizure to seizure, in terms of duration and severity of the occurrence. Various treatment options for this disease have been studied and put into practice, being still subjected to limitations. The most widely adopted treatment is drug therapy; however, approximately 30% of the patients are drug-resistant. Another technique is ablation surgery for which only 7% to 8% of patients are suitable [1], given the risks of surgical resection and the particular area of the brain needed to be targeted in each patient.

Electrical stimulation to terminate emerging seizures is regarded as a new option for epilepsy treatment. To implement this approach, rapid and accurate seizure detection counting on intracranial electroencephalography (iEEG) signals is

needed [2]. Early detection would allow a successful neural stimulation or drug delivery that could avoid numerous complications including sudden falls, drowning, car accidents, and suicidal tendencies.

Different challenges such as extracting a suitable group of features in conjunction with a selection of an optimal classifier must be overcome with the purpose of making this approach efficient for numerous patients. Feature types are categorized according to their signal processing domain. The time-domain features exhibit low computational complexity compared to frequency-domain features that is extremely essential for low-power hardware implementation of implantable devices [3]. [4] extracts time-domain local binary patterns (*LBP*) with hyperdimensional (*HD*) computing classification using iEEG signals. However, relying on a single *LBP* feature does not contribute to an outstanding detection performance for all tested patients. Furthermore, the hardware implementation of *HD* classifier is not performed. [5] extracts Line-length, energy and nonlinear energy time-domain features in a two-stage architecture to provide a low-power feature extraction method. [3] presents patient-specific channel and feature selection approaches based on time-domain features that are highly suitable for accurate and low-complexity seizure detection. However, [3], [4] and [5] do not perform hardware implementation of a machine learning classifier that is compatible with seizure detector implants.

Various type of classifiers for seizure detection have already been examined in order to distinguish between ictal and non-ictal states. Support Vector Machines (*SVM*) classifiers correspond to the most used in the literature [6]–[8]. Although they show excellent performance in terms of accuracy and in particular, specificity, their limiting factor lies in the detection latency of the seizure detection, which is higher compared to other classification methods. The latest research works show better performance of the Random Forest classifier compared to the *SVM*, particularly in terms of detection latency [1], [9].

In this work, three low-complexity time-domain features are selected to be employed in the feature extraction block. In addition, a comprehensive comparison between two widely used classifiers is conducted to choose the best candidate for seizure detection from iEEG signals both in terms of seizure detection performance and classifier hyperparameters. The hardware implementation of the feature extractor and classifier units is realized on an FPGA to obtain the experimental results

TABLE I: Patients information

Patient	Age[y]	Num of seizures	Num of electrodes	Mean duration of seizures(s)
ID1	46	13	47	71
ID2	48	4	42	223
ID3	32	2	98	99
ID4	19	14	62	112
ID5	31	10	54	99
ID6	31	4	64	146

Fig. 1: Block diagram of the system architecture

of the tested subjects.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Section II describes the topology of the proposed seizure detection system and introduces the iEEG dataset from the Bern University Hospital. Section III explain details regarding features which are extracted in the digital signal processing unit. Section IV compares the performance of two widely-used classifiers and optimized the selected classifier to be implemented on a hardware. The FPGA implementation results of the seizure detector are given in Section V. Finally, the main outcomes of this paper are summed up in Section VI.

II. MATERIALS AND SYSTEM TOPOLOGY

A. iEEG database

The publicly available SWEC-ETHZ iEEG dataset has been the source used throughout this article. In particular, the part of the short-term dataset of EEG signals recorded intracranially by strip, grid, and depth electrodes at Bern University Hospital for 16 patients has been utilized. These signals were recorded and analysed during pre-surgical evaluations of patients with pharmaco-resistant epilepsy. Currently, intracranial electroencephalography (iEEG) provides the best spatial resolution and the highest signal-to-noise ratio to record the brain activity in patients with epilepsy. It should be noted that the short-term dataset contains a 3-second pre-ictal and a 3-minute post-ictal iEEG signals for all seizure occurrences [4]. The iEEG signals are sampled at 512 Hz. Some details regarding the patients that are tested in this work are given in Table I.

B. Seizure detection system topology

Digitized iEEG signals are the input of the digital signal processor (DSP) of the seizure detector. The DSP outputs are forwarded to a classifier to make a binary classification. The block diagram of a machine learning-based seizure detector is depicted in Fig. 1.

The digitized iEEG input is acquired through multichannel recording sites at 512 Hz. Signal segmentation has been performed in 1-second windows in order to extract time-domain features. The window length has been selected

considering the tradeoff between classification stability and detection latency. The average value of multichannel iEEG data is given to the digital signal processor. The digital signal processor extracts three time-domain features and feeds the classifier. Binary classification is carried out to detect patients' status.

III. FEATURE EXTRACTION

The digital signal processing (DSP) block executes feature extraction in which the discriminating features for seizure detection are extracted and given to a classification unit for further processing. Three time-domain features are chosen to be employed after studying the performance of various time-domain features on SVM and Random Forest classifiers. Moreover, line length, variance and range features performed better considering the feature importance factor in random forest classification.

A. Line length

The line length feature represents an alteration of the waveform dimensionality, as well as being a measure sensitive to variation of the signal amplitude and frequency. It also presents a low computational cost that is convenient for hardware implementation. The line length equation is given in (1).

$$LL = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N |x_{i+1} - x_i| \quad (1)$$

Where N is the number of samples in a window and x_i is the i^{th} sample of a window.

B. Variance

The variance is a measure of the deviation of the signal from its mean value. Therefore, it is highly beneficial to demonstrate abnormal brain activity. The variance equation is given in (2).

$$VAR = \frac{1}{N-1} \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} (x_i - \mu)^2 \quad (2)$$

C. Range

Another widely adopted time-domain feature is the range metric, which presents a high variance from seizure to non-seizure state of the brain. The range feature definition is given in (3).

$$RNG = \max(x_i) - \min(x_i) \quad (3)$$

The value of the mentioned extracted features are computed in each 1-sec window and directed to the classification block that is explained in Section IV.

IV. CLASSIFICATION

A comparison between two widely-used classifiers is done using the features introduced in the previous section. Subsequently, the superior classifier is selected to be implemented on an FPGA that is described hereafter.

TABLE II: Classifiers comparison results

Patient Classifier	ID1		ID2		ID3	
	RF	SVM	RF	SVM	RF	SVM
AUC	0.88	0.15	0.98	0.92	0.96	0.87
Sensitivity	1	1	1	1	1	1
Specificity	0.94	0.95	0.94	0.89	0.96	0.99
Accuracy	0.6	0.58	0.97	0.94	0.95	0.95
Delay	3.3	12	0	0	3	4

Fig. 2: Topology of the random forest implementation

A. Classifier selection

According to the state-of-the-art literature review, the classifier selection was narrowed down to Random Forest and linear SVM classifiers, given their outstanding results and, in particular, their relatively low complexity, which made them appropriate candidates for FPGA implementation [1], [6]–[9]. Multiple classification and seizure detection metrics are taken into account to offer a fair comparison between seizure detection by SVM and Random Forest classifiers.

Both classifiers are trained with their hyperparameters optimized so as to detect seizures from line length, variance, and range features. The classifiers performance is assessed by the Receiver Operating Characteristic curve (ROC) and its resulting Area Under the Curve (AUC), that provide an overall comparison method to evaluate the quality of a classifier.

Furthermore, four significant seizure detection metrics are defined as 1) sensitivity, 2) specificity, 3) accuracy, and 4) detection delay. iEEG signals of three patients from the Bern University Hospital are utilized to evaluate the performance of these two classifiers to select the best candidate. The *MATLAB* simulation results are given in Table II.

Table II reveals that both classifiers could reach 100% sensitivity in seizure detection. Furthermore, the Random Forest classifier outperforms the linear SVM classifier in terms of AUC, specificity, accuracy and delay. Thus, the Random Forest classifier is chosen to be utilized in the rest of this paper. An overview of the Random Forest classifier architecture is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 3: Classification accuracy with respect to the number of decision nodes

B. Random Forest classifier

A Random Forest classifier consists of multiple decision trees, whose outputs undergo majority voting, leading to the final prediction value of the ensemble. Trees are grown using binary decisions at the so-called decision nodes. When classifying a sample, it travels down the tree through a path given by the decision nodes which ends up at a leaf responsible for its classification.

The randomness of the classifier lies in two aspects. The first is that trees in the forest are grown from bootstrap samples extracted from a random subset of the trained data. Secondly, only a random subgroup of the predictors (signal features) are used at decision splits of each tree. After this random process, train samples not included in the subset used to construct the trees of the forest are called Out-of-Bag units, which can be used to evaluate and calibrate the performance of each tree [1]. In the presented method, feature importance are estimated by evaluating which trees (and features used in their decision nodes) performed better in this Out-of-Bag subset of samples. The line length, variance and range features are selected at this stage.

The tree's depth and the number of trees in each forest are regarded as two substantial hyperparameters of a random forest classifier. The depth of the trees directly depends on the number of decision nodes. This number should be low to avoid over-fitting, as a too detailed match of trained samples characteristics in the trees would lead to wrong classifications of test samples that differ slightly in some feature values. The lower complexity of the algorithm comes along as a side advantage of this low depth. On the other hand, a sufficient number of decision nodes is required to guarantee high sensitivity and specificity of the classifier. Hence, experiments led to an optimal number of three decision nodes as demonstrated in Fig. 3. It can be observed that as the number of decision nodes increases from one to three, the seizure detection accuracy is improved. In addition, as the number of decision nodes increases from three, the accuracy is degraded from the maximum value.

A trade-off exists between classification overfitting and computation complexity (number of required resources, training and test time) to find the optimal number of trees. Fig. 4 depicts the Out-of-Bag classification error for different number of trees. The ideal value is found to be 20. Nevertheless, the number of trees is limited to five due

Fig. 4: RF performance for different number of decision trees

TABLE III: Hardware implementation parameters

Operating frequency	512 Hz	Memory (Kb)	232.115
Logic utilization	1475	DSP blocks	4
Num of registers	2297	Dynamic power (mW)	0.59

to hardware implementation limitations such as keeping the number of resources as low as possible while the detection performance is not remarkably affected.

V. HARDWARE IMPLEMENTATION RESULTS

The presented seizure detection method using three time-domain features and a Random Forest classifier is implemented on the Cyclone V FPGA of an ALTERA DE10-Standard board. Table III contains the main FPGA implementation parameters considering the average FPGA implementation results of six subjects.

Recorded signals of six patients with short-term seizure periods from the SWEC-ETHZ dataset are utilized to evaluate the performance of the system. Table IV includes the performance metrics of the system as well as the power consumption reported for each patient individually. It evidences that 100% detection sensitivity is reached for all patients while the majority of the patients exhibit over 98% and below 10 sec accuracy and detection latency, respectively.

Moreover, Table V compares the FPGA implementation results with two recently published articles that employed random forest classification. Table V indicates that this work reaches 100% sensitivity as [9], that is better than [4]. Furthermore, our proposed machine learning-based seizure detector outperforms [9] and [4] in terms of all performance metrics such as specificity, accuracy, and detection latency. It is noteworthy that the hardware FPGA implementation results are reported in this work while [9] and [4] results are only based on software simulation.

VI. CONCLUSION

A machine learning-based epileptic seizure detector using a hardware-friendly architecture of a random forest classifier is developed and implemented on a Cyclone V FPGA. A comparison is performed between the Random Forest classifier and the linear SVM classifier that reveals the superiority of the Random Forest classifier using iEEG signals with identical

TABLE IV: FPGA implementation results

Patient	Sensitivity	Specificity	Accuracy	Delay (s)	Power (mW)
ID1	100	95.21	97.6	11	0.60
ID2	100	98.61	99.31	0	0.58
ID3	100	99.72	99.86	3	0.60
ID4a	100	95.14	97.57	5.5	0.61
ID4b	100	82.78	91.39	46	0.59
ID5	100	97.78	98.89	12	0.58
ID6	100	97.50	98.75	5	0.59

TABLE V: Comparison with the state-of-the-art

	[4]'2020	[9]'2020	This work
Dataset	SWEC-ETHZ	[9]	SWEC-ETHZ
Hardware	No	No	Yes (FPGA)
Sensitivity	94.94	100	100
Specificity	95.53	94.16	95.57
Accuracy	95.24	97.08	97.78
Delay (s)	15.09	17.03	11.78
Power (mW)	n.a	n.a	0.59

features over the SVM classifier. Subsequently, the significant hyperparameters of the Random Forest classifier are optimized not only to obtain the highest detection performance but also to offer a design that is compatible with low-power resource-constraint hardware implementation. Line length, variance, and range features, which obtained the highest feature importance in random forest classification, are selected to be extracted in the DSP unit. The FPGA implementation of the proposed method is tested on six patients from the SWEC-ETHZ database that demonstrates the perfect sensitivity of 100%, and superior performance compared to the literature in terms of the seizure detection accuracy and latency thanks to our novel low-complexity implementation of the Random Forest classifier which consumes only 0.59 mW dynamic power.

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